

S-Chloro-N-Phenyl Thiocarbamoyl Chloride as an Intermediate in Heterocyclic Synthesis

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It has been shown in an earlier communication^{1,2} that 1,2,4-dithiazolidines with thion and substituted imino groups in position 3, 5 respectively and with or without³ substituents at position 4 can be easily synthesized by the interaction of S-Chloro-N-aryl thiocarbamoyl chloride with appropriate dithiocarbamate⁴s. Thus

- where (a) R=R'=Phenyl, *p*-Cl-phenyl, *p*-tolyl.
 (b) R=Phenyl, *p*-Cl-phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl, cyclohexyl, methyl and benzyl, and R'=Phenyl, *p*-Cl-phenyl, *p*-tolyl.
 (c) R=H, R'=Phenyl.

Extension of the reaction to phenyl thiocarbamide if it followed the above route of reaction, was expected to afford II/III.

With this end in view a mixture of phenyl thiocarbamide (8.0 g) and S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (20.0 g) in dry benzene (200 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hrs when H₂S and HCl were liberated. The sticky yellow residue obtained on distilling off benzene was heated with boiling ethanol. On filtering out the free elemental sulphur that had separated the ethanolic extract was basified with dil. ammonia when a viscous oil separated which on repeated trituration with petroleum ether followed by ethanol afforded a solid (9.0 g); crystallised from chlorobenzene/glacial acetic acid, m.p.220°, (Found: C, 64.57; H, 4.55; N, 14.73; S, 15.98; C₂₁H₁₆N₄S₂ requires: C, 64.94; H, 4.12; N, 14.43; S, 16.59%.)

The compound on refluxing with benzyl chloride in an ethanolic medium afforded a colourless hydrochloride (V) m.p.172° Found: Mol. Eq. 508.5; C₂₈H₂₃N₄S₂·HCl requires: Mol. Eq. 516.5). On hydrolysis with conc. hydrochloric acid the PhN= was cleaved off affording (VI), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 56.95; H, 3.35; N, 13.20; C₁₅H₁₁N₃S₂O requires; C, 57.51; H, 3.52; N, 13.42%.)

The IR spectrum of the compound IV; where R=R'=phenyl) showed the presence of cyclic-NH and C=N at 3225 and 1675 cm⁻¹ respectively. The band at 1060 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of C=S and another band at 1540 cm⁻¹ was most probably due to 1,3,5-triazine ring system. A medium intensity band at 780 cm⁻¹ probably indicated the presence of isotriazine ring⁴.

On the basis of above facts the compound with m.p. 220° has been assigned the structure: 1,3-diphenyl-2,4-dithio-6-phenylimino-1, 3, 5 hexahydro triazine (IVa)⁵.

- where (a) R = R'=Phenyl
 (b) R=*p*-Cl-phenyl, R' = phenyl

It is evident, that in the reaction leading to (IV), two moles of S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and one molecule of phenyl thiocarbamide have participated. Since elemental sulphur is eliminated during the reaction as also H₂S and HCl it follows that more than one intermediate steps (products) must be involved and one of these must be a disulphide. But the high yield of (IV) is suggestive of the reaction being not just a side reaction.

S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (20.0 g) also reacted with *p*-Cl-phenyl thiocarbamide (10.0 g) in refluxing benzene medium (200 ml) and afforded a product, m. p. 218° (Found: N, 13.41; S, 14.89; C₂₁H₁₆N₄S₂Cl requires: N, 13.25; S, 15.14%) which has been assigned the structure (IVb).

Further work is proposed to be undertaken to locate the intermediates and elucidate the mechanism.

The required S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride was prepared by the method described earlier⁶. The phenyl/*p*-Cl-phenyl thiocarbamides were prepared by the interaction of an appropriate amine hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate⁷.

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NOTES

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**Search for Potential Antiviral Drugs.
Part I. Synthesis of Substituted
Butyrophenone Thiosemicarbazones**

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ANTI-viral activity of thiosemicarbazones has been confirmed by many workers¹⁻⁹. *In vitro* inhibition of APR-8 and vaccinia viruses has been claimed for a few biphenyl derivatives^{1,0}. Moreover, propiophenones have been shown to exert viricidal effect against Ranikhet disease virus in chlorioallantoic membrane^{1,1}.

A few newer thiosemicarbazones incorporating the active biphenyl moiety have now been synthesised with a view to study their antiviral properties.

4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl butyrophenones (I) were obtained by condensing N-substituted piperazines with 4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -chloro butyrophenone.

Thiosemicarbazones (II) described in this communication were obtained by treating the butyrophenones (I) with appropriate N-aryl thiosemicarbazides.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

(A) *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl-butyrophenones :

A mixture of *p*-(*p*-acetamidophenyl)- γ -chloro-butyrophenone (.02 mole), an appropriate piperazine^{1,1,1,2} (.02 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol for 24 hrs. At the end of this period the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated several times with hot water. The crude product so obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

R, m. p. and other data are recorded in Table 1.

S. No.	R	m.p. C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Calcd %N	Found %N
1.	-CH ₃	152	65	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂	11.08	10.98
2.	-Ph	148	60	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ N ₃ O ₂	9.52	9.44
3.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	170	61	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ N ₃ O ₂	9.23	9.12

(B) *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl butyrophenone thiosemicarbazones :

A solution of *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ substituted piperazinyl butyrophenone (.002 mole) in ethanol (containing one drop of conc. HCl) was mixed with the solution of appropriate aryl thiosemicarbazide^o (.002 mole) in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for 6-8 hrs. After concentration and cooling a solid mass separated out which was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

R, R', m. p. and other data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl No	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Calcd %N	Found %N
1.	-CH ₃	H	179	C ₃₀ H ₃₆ N ₆ OS	15.99	15.54
2.	-CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	182	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	15.50	15.28
3.	-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	190	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	15.50	15.12
4.	-CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	192	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	15.05	14.64
5.	-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	15.05	14.56
6.	-Ph	-H	176	C ₃₅ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	14.23	13.98
7.	-Ph	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	152	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.90	13.48
8.	-Ph	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	165	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.90	13.62
9.	-Ph	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.55	13.26
10.	-Ph	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	179	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.55	13.18
11.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	H	195	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.33	13.24
12.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	200	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ OS	13.04	12.94
13.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ OS	13.04	12.88
14.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	12.72	12.46
15.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	215	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	12.72	12.54

These compounds were obtained in 60-70% yield.